

The History and Transformation of Yoga Services: From Ancient Traditions to Modern Wellness Practices

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DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.15501733

Abstract:

Yog this word derived from the Sanskrit word 'Yuj' means to get Join. Self must get join to other self, society, nature and then at last to the higher self. Yoga, an ancient discipline originating in Bharat, has evolved over millennia from a spiritual practice to a globally recognized wellness service. Allopathy medicines provide temporary benefit and dangerous side effects So people are looking towards yoga therapy as a better health treatment. Today, yoga centers are being established all over the world. Yoga is becoming popular. Therefore, Yoga services have become commercialized in various modern forms like Power Yoga, Hot yoga, Yin Yoga, Prenatal yoga, Chair yoga etc. Spiritual organizations are also emphasizing Karma Yoga of Bhagavad Gita. Overall 'yoga' is becoming popular. Many Scholars are studying yoga from a philosophical and spiritual point of view. In short, yoga has a bright future. 'Yoga' is becoming a very popular subject today. Yoga is also gaining recognition globally. Even in advanced countries like America, thousands Yoga centers have been established. Patanjali Rishi is getting fame all over the world. 'yoga' was in existence before the great Patanjali Rishi. The philosophy of Patanjali gave it a proper form. Patanjali Rishi formulated Around 194-95 Yog Sutras. These Yoga Sutras are divided into four chapters. Patanjali Yoga is called as a Raja Yoga in general. There are many aspects of yoga found in the past as well as now for example Mantra Yoga, Lay Yoga, Jnana Yoga, Bhakti Yoga, Jnanyoga, Karmayoga etc. The historical study of these Yoga will be very enlightening. There are many misconceptions about yoga that Yoga is a magic, miracles or witchcraft. This paper explores the historical development of yoga, examining its origins, philosophical foundations, and transformation into a modern service industry. The paper also analyses the factors contributing to the growth of yoga services, including globalization, scientific validation, and the increasing demand for holistic health solutions. The research insights into the future trajectory of yoga services, emphasizing the need for preserving its authentic essence amidst commercialization through customised yoga services of yoga Centre

Keywords: Yog/Yoga, Ved, Upanishad, Rajyog, Healthcare

Introduction:

इमं विवस्वते योगं प्रोक्तवानहमव्ययम् ।

विवस्वान्मनवे प्राह मनुर्दिक्वाकवेऽब्रवीत् ॥

(Bhagavad Gita 4.1)

Lord Shri Krishna says, “At very first I taught this Yoga to the Vivasvan- Source of energy the Sun, who passed it on to Rajarshi Manu, and then Rushi Manu instructed it to Raja Ikshvaku” Pandit

Satvalekar interpret Vivasvan as a Legacy of brave and Suryavashi king in which King Ishwaku and King Rama developed.

एवं परम्पराप्राप्तमिमं राजर्षयो विदुः।

स कालेनेह महता योगो नष्टः परन्तप ॥

(Bhagavad Gita 4.2)

Lord Shri Krishna says, “O Parantapa (Arjuna) This Yog, thus received through a traditional Legacy, was known by the royal sages (Rajarshis); but with the passage of

great time, it has been lost” Georg Feuerstein historically made the six stages of development of yoga from first stage proto-yoga to Modern Yoga as a last stage. Yoga, a practice with roots in ancient India, has become a global phenomenon, transcending cultural and geographical boundaries. Originally a spiritual discipline aimed at achieving self-realization, yoga has undergone significant transformations, evolving into a multifaceted service industry. This paper aims to trace the historical development of yoga, examining its journey from ancient traditions to contemporary wellness practices.

History of Yoga:

Vaidic Yoga Period:

Discoveries of figures in yoga-like postures in the Indus Valley Civilization shows the existence of yoga in Bharat in Vaidic Period. The most primitive written document of yoga found in the *Rigveda*, one of the oldest sacred Vaidic texts in the world (Feuerstein). *Hiranyagarbha Sukta* are found in Veda which describes *Hiranyagarbha* as the origin of Yoga. *हिरण्यगर्भः समवर्तताग्रं भूतस्य जातः पतिरेकं आसीत् (Rugved, 10.121.1)*. Feuerstein’s Proto yoga explains the routes of yoga in *Mantrasamhita* of Veda (Feuerstein). *Dirghatama Rushi* in one *Sukta of Rugveda* says “I saw Prana coming inside and outside the body through various ways and protecting all organs of the body”. (45.1.164.31). Ishavasyopadishad (*ShuklaYajurvedaAdhyay 40*) give the reference of *Soham mantra* which is popularly used in *Yog Sadhana* today also.

Classical Yoga Period:

Over time, the practice of yoga was systematized in the *Upanishads*. Feuerstein’s consider it as an *Upanishadic Yog*. Upanishad means understanding knowledge through residing near the feet of the Guru. Every Upanishad start with Shanti Mantra ॐ सह नाववतु सह नौ भुनक्तु सह वीर्यं करवावहौ

तेजस्वि नावधीतमस्तु मा विदविश्वैः ॐ शान्तिः शान्तिः शान्तिः ॥ in this shanti mantra ॐ itself symbol of yog. Student and teacher are learning through joining psychologically with each other. This is a *yog* in between teacher and student. Following important *Upanishads* having *Yog* as *Adwitawadi* and Theist Base. *Isha Upanishad, Ken Upanishad, Kath Upanishad, Chandogya Upanishad, Prashna Upanishad, Mundak Upanishad, Mandukya Upanishad, Aietarey Upanishad, Taitarey Upanishad, Bruhadaranyak Upanishad, Kaushiktey Upanishad, Maitrayani Upanishad, Shwetashwetar Upanishad*. All these Upanishad consider *Yog* means merging with supernatural Power. All these focus on *Dhyan* instead of following rituals. *Shwetashwetar Upanishad* is the Locus of *Yoga (R.D. Ranade)* *Valmiki Rishi* wrote epic the *Rāmāyana*. *Rishi Vyasa* wrote the *Mahābhārata*. This is known as “Epic *Yoga* Age”. *Shri Ram* in his journey of *Vanvas* spread *yoga* practices between various *rishis* and common people. This might be the main purpose of *Ram* and *Vasishta* behind *Vanvas* as per the interpretation of *Rev. Pandurang Shatri Aathavale*. *Shri Ram* informed actual *yoga* un to the last in his Period of *vanvas*. *Mahabharat* epic is divided into 18 Parts known as 18 Parva. *Shrimad Bhagavad Gītā* as a *yogshatra* is a part of *Bhishma Parva* of *Mahābhārata*. *Shrimad Bhagavad Gītā* is a popular *Yogshatra*.

तपस्विभ्योऽधिको योगी ज्ञानिभ्योऽपि मतोऽधिकः।

कर्मिभ्यश्चाधिको योगी तस्माद्भोगी भवार्जुनः ॥(Bhagavad Gita 6.46)

Krishna insists *Arjuna* to be a *Yogi* as *yogi* is above all. *Shrimad Bhagavad Gītā* divided into 18 Chapters known as *Adhyay*. All *Adhyay* is known as different *Yogashatra* as follows *ArjunaViṣhāda Yoga, Sankhya Yoga, Karma Yoga, Jnana Yoga, KarmaSanyāsa Yoga, Dhyāna Yoga, Vijnana Yoga, AkṣharaParabrahmaYoga, RājaVidyā Yoga, Vibhūti Yoga, ViṣhwarūpDarśhana Yoga,*

*Bhakti Yoga, KṣhetraKṣhetrajñaVibhāga
Yoga, GuṇaTrayaVibhāga Yoga,
Puruṣhottama Yoga,
DaivāsuraSampadVibhāga Yoga,
ŚhraddhāTrayaVibhāga Yoga,
MokṣhaSanyāsa Yoga.*

Medieval Period:

*योगेन चित्तस्य पदेन वाचां मलं शरीरस्य च वैद्यकेना॥
योऽपाकरोत् प्रवरं मुनीनां पतञ्जलिं प्राञ्जलिरानतोऽस्मि॥
(Lokokti)*

Patanjali's Yoga Sutras are the main sutras of this period popularly known as classical yoga. Patanjali Muni was a great linguist, doctor and yogi. He started yogshastra with Sutra अथ योगानुशासनम् (*Yoga Sutras 1.1*). He defined yoga as योगश्चित्तवृत्तिनिरोधः (*Yoga Sutras 1.2*). He taught Ashtanga Yoga to reach *Asaprajnat or Nirvikalpasamadhi*. Yama, Niyama, Asana, Pranayama, Pratyahara, Dharana, Dhyana and Samadhi are the eight limbs of Patanjali Yoga. It is also called Raja Yoga. There are 195 Yoga Sutras in total and they are divided into four chapters. 1) *Samadhipada* 2) *Sadhanapada* 3) *Vibhutipada* 4) *Kaivalyapada*. Personal morality is very important in Ashtanga Yoga. Ten ethical principles are included with five *Yama* and *Niyama*.

*अहिंसासत्यास्तेयब्रह्मचर्यापिरीग्रहा यमाः॥
शौचसंतोषतपःस्वाध्यायेश्वरप्रणिधानानि नियमाः॥ (Yogutras 2.30,32).* Gautam Buddha and Mahaveer also preached some of these ethical principles of yoga. Aasan & Pranayam comes after the *Yama* and *Niyama*. A Sadhak traveling on the path of yoga must be morally endowed with character. Surprisingly, '*Ishwar Pranidhana*' is also given a place in it. स पूर्वेषामपि गुरुः कालेनानवच्छेदात् तस्य वाचकः प्रणवः॥ (*Yogutras 1.26,27*). Ishvara is an ancient teacher, beyond time and designated as ॐ. True yoga is the applied science of mind control, concentration and happiness. Psychologically relevant remedies for 'concentrating' the mind are given. According to the sutra '*Deshbandhachittasyadharana*', Patanjali has

given the key to concentrate the mind in a holy and noble place. Patanjali preaches: *Abhyasvairagyabhyas Nirodha*. Shreemadbhagvadgeta also stresses on *abhyas and vairagya* to control the mind. *Abhyas* means *Sadhana* and *Vairagya* means non-attachment to material values. Following yog upanishadas came in existence after the Yoga Sutras. *Advayataraka, Amritanada, Amritabindu, Brahmailydia, Darshan, Dhyanaibindu, Hamsa, Kshurika, Mahavakya, Mandalabrahmana, Nadabindu, Tejobindu, Yogachudamani, Yogakundali, Yogaraja, Yogashikha, Yogatarava, Shandilya, Pashupatabrahma, and Varāhu Trishikhi-Brahmana*. In the *Yogakundali Upanishad, Kundalini* Yoga is explained from the viewpoint of Advaita Vedanta. In the *Yogaraja Upanishads*, alongside *Layayoga*, there is also consideration of the chakras. To put it briefly, yogic thoughts based on *Vedanta* are presented in the *Yoga Upanishads*. Primarily, this includes an emphasis on *Hatha Yoga and Kundalini* Yoga. In the *Hatha* Ha means the Sun and Tha means the moon are the symbol of duality. Attaining balance in this duality is *Hatha* Yoga by awakening *Kundalini*. During this period, Tantric knowledge developed. In this field, the concept of '*Shakti* (Goddess)' is at centre. Through tantric practices, one seeks the assistance of this *Shakti* for attaining liberation. Along with the external worship of the Goddess, greater emphasis is placed on *Kundalini* Yoga. Our body is not to be considered contemptible or dispensable; it is the residence of the Goddess and a valuable tool for liberation. The Tantric path includes three paths: 1) The *Dakshinamarga* is the traditional *Tantric* path. 2) *Vamamarga* uses the five 'M.' known as *Panchmukhi* 3) *Kulamarga* (*Kaula Sampradayamarga*). Consumption of alcohol, meat, fish, mudra, and maithuna is prescribed in the *Vamamarga*. The consumption of the first

four stimulates worldly desires. By activating the stored sexual energy, one reaches the peak of enjoyment in maithuna. However, this path is dangerous. *Hatha Yoga* or *Hatha Vidya* is more prevalent in the *Kanphata* sect. In fact, *Gorakshanath* (9th-10th century) is considered the originator of this yoga. In the Nath sect, the body is given more emphasis as a means of yogic practice. *Hatha Yoga* insists on transforming the ordinary body into a 'Yogic body'. *Hatha Yoga* is a process to convert the common body into the 'Yoga body.' In *Gorakshanath's Siddhasiddhanta* philosophy, the philosophy of the body is discussed in detail (*Nigal*). The true goal of *Hatha Yoga* is to establish unity between the *Kundalini* energy and Shiva in the *Sahasrara chakra*. In this unity, the experience of *Nirvikalpa samadhi* occurs. The *HathYog Pradipika*, written by *Swatmarama* in the 15th century, is renowned on this subject. According to *Swatmarama*, *Layayoga* is achieved through *Nada-upasana*. *Gorakshashatakam Shadangyog* (*Asana, Pranayama, Pratyahara, Dharana, Dhyana, Samadhi*), *Hathayogapradipika* emphasizes *Chaturangyog* (*Asana, Pranayama, Mudra, Bandha*), *Gheranda* emphasizes *Saptangayoga*. (*Shatkarma, Asana, Mudra, Pratyahara, Pranayama, Dhyana, Samadhi*) *Gorksha Samhita* explain three types of pranayama *Purak, kumbhak and Rechak* with ratio of 12:16:10 instead of traditional ratio 1:4:2. *HathYog* explain *shatkarm* means six body cleansing procedure

Modern Period:

The works of *Ramkrishna Paramhansa, Swami Vivekananda and Yogi Arvind Ghosh* are mainly remembered during the last half of the 19th century and the first half of the 20th century. *Swami Vivekananda* gave lectures on *Yoga Sutras* in America on *Jnana Yoga, Karma Yoga, Bhakti Yoga and Raja Yoga* etc. His commentaries on yoga are famous. *Yogi*

Arvind Ghosh (1872-1950 AD) was the exponent of Integral Yoga. One of his books is also titled: 'Synthesis of Yoga' He wants to coordinate the salvation of the individual and the evolutionary destiny of humanity. It requires traveling from the mental level to the supramental level. This journey is internal. In his words, It is a transition from the mental to the Supramental Consciousness. In this yogic development, not only the development of the individual but also the spiritual level of the society is raised along with the individual. 'The Society of Gnostic Beings', as *Aurobindo Babu's* calls it, can emerge. The flourishing of such spiritual seekers leads to the invention or descent of divine powers. (Ascent of man & Descent of Supermind) also by *Paramahansa Yogananda* (1893-1952 AD a disciple of *Muktasara Spread 'Kriya Yoga'* in America. In 1920, he founded the Self-Realization Fellowship. He published his autobiography in 1946. (*Autobiography of a Yogi*) It became very popular. *Yogananda* also got a lot of fame. *Swami Sivananda* (1887 to 1963) was a doctor by profession. In the year 1923, he started an organization called 'Divine Life Samaj'. *Swami Chidananda, Swami Shivananda Radha and Swami Satyananda* were his disciple. *Swami Satyananda* founded *Biharyoga* (Munger). *Swami Shivananda Radha* a German woman, went to Canada and established *Yog Centre*. *Kuvalayananda* established a yoga centre at *Lonavla*. This center looks at yoga scientifically and keeps a proper record of all the practitioners. Transcendental Meditation technique of *Mahesh Yogi (Maharishi)* has got millions of followers worldwide.

Twentieth Century Yoga:

Sri Sri Ravi Shankarji is one of the disciples of *Maharishi Mahesh Yogi* spread yoga. He drafted the proposal for International Meditation Day. Thousands of yoga centers have been established in India

and outside India in the Twentieth Century. The approach of most of these centers is pragmatic. 'Yoga for health or wellness' is the mantra of most of these centres. Not only this, yoga is seen as 'a healing modality'. *Yoga Service* became a commercial and business one. Crores of dollars are traded in connection with yoga. *Yoga mats, yoga bags, yoga shirts, Yoga bricks and Yoga equipment* are given more importance by many centres. *Yoga postures, Pratyahara and Pranayama* can be particularly useful as preventive measures. *BKS Iyengar* cured many neurological disorders of the famous violinist *Shri Yehudi Menuhin* through yoga therapy. As a result, yoga became popular in the western world as well. Iyengar went to Switzerland at the invitation of *Yehudi Menuhin*. There he taught yoga to many musicians. Today, *yoga centers* are being established all over the world. *Yoga* is becoming popular. So, yoga is getting commercialized. Although taking allopathic medicines gives temporary relief, its side effects are also dangerous. People are looking at yoga therapy as a different form of therapy (Nigal S.G). *Baba Ramdev* used television to the spread yoga and encouraged millions to practice yoga for health by holding yoga camps. Athletes are also starting to feel the need for yoga. Overall Yoga is gaining popularity. Scholars who study yoga from a philosophical and spiritual point of view are also coming forward. *Sadguru Jaggi Vasudev* convinced logically and scientifically the relevance of yoga to scholars of the world. He formed the Institute Adiyog and started residential yoga camp. *Yog vidya dham* in Nashik formed by *Yogguru Vishvas Mandalik* running various courses like *Yog Pravesh, Yog Shishak, Yog Prabodh, Yog Adhyapak, etc.* Almost every university is running *yoga* related certificate courses now. NEP 2020 introducing Indian Knowledge System (IKS) and *Yoga* education subject at school and graduation level. On 21st June 2024 the world

consequently celebrated tenth International *Yoga Day*. In short, yoga has a bright future.

TRANSFORMATION OF YOGA SERVICES:

ANCIENT TRADITIONS OF YOGA

Modern Wellness Practices Of Yoga Services:

Iyengar yoga	Vinyasa yoga	Bikram Yoga	Power yoga	Restorative yoga
Hot yoga	Yin yoga	Yoga for Migraine	Paddleboard yoga	Chair yoga
Prenatal yoga	Yoga for thyroid	Yoga for Asthma	Yoga for Cervical	Yoga for diabetics
Online Yoga	Yoga for Kids	Yoga for Women	Yoga for men	Yoga for Eyes
Yoga for Arthritis	Yoga for Height	Yoga for PCOS/P COD	Yoga for Acidity	Yoga for heart
Yoga for Skin	Aerial yoga	Yoga for senior citizens	Yoga for hair loss	Home yoga

The Evolution of Yoga as A Service: Globalization and Popularization:

The globalization of yoga began in the mid-20th century, as Western interest in Eastern spirituality grew. Yoga was increasingly marketed as a health and fitness practice, leading to the establishment of yoga studios, teacher training programs, and wellness retreats worldwide. The rise of mass media and the internet further accelerated the spread of yoga, making it accessible to a global audience.

Commercialization and Professionalization:

As yoga gained popularity, it also became a lucrative industry, with the emergence of branded yoga styles, apparel, and accessories. The professionalization of yoga services led to the creation of certification programs, governing bodies, and standards for yoga instruction. However, this commercialization has raised concerns about the dilution of yoga's spiritual essence

and the commodification of a sacred tradition.

Scientific Validation and Integration into Healthcare:

In recent decades, scientific research has validated the health benefits of yoga, leading to its integration into mainstream healthcare and wellness programs. Yoga is now widely recognized as an effective intervention for stress management, chronic pain, mental health disorders, and overall well-being. This shift has further expanded the scope of yoga services, with a growing number of healthcare professionals incorporating yoga into their practice.

Conclusion:

Yog this word derived from the word 'Yuj' means to get Join. Self must get join to other self at first and then at last to the higher self is a *Yog*. Function of three H of a human organ- Hand (all body organs), Head (intellect) and Heart (feeling) of a man must get join to each other is a *Yog*. To reduce the differences between man Verses man, Society and man verses Nature is a *yog*. *Yoga* historically emerged from Ved, *upanishad*, epics, classical, medieval, modern period and developed professionally in twentieth century. Today, yoga centres are being established all over the world. *Yoga* is becoming popular. So, *yoga* is getting commercialized. Although taking allopathic medicines gives quick temporary relief, its side effects are dangerous. People are looking at *yoga* therapy as a different form of therapy. *Baba Ramdev* used television to the spread *yoga* and encouraged millions to practice *yoga* for health by holding *yoga* camps. Athletes are also starting to feel the need for *yoga*. Overall *Yoga* is gaining popularity. Scholars who study *yoga* from a philosophical and spiritual point of view are also coming forward. In short, *yoga* has a bright future. The history and development of *yoga* services reflect the dynamic interplay between tradition and modernity.

While *yoga* has evolved into a global wellness service, its essence as a spiritual practice should remain at its core. As the industry continues to grow, it is essential to balance innovation with authenticity, ensuring that *yoga* remains a transformative and accessible practice for all and with the passage of great time, it should not be lost in future.

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